

Understanding practices in an interdisciplinary group from a case study

Elizabeth Suazo-Flores, Purdue University, esuazo@purdue.edu

William S. Walker III, Purdue University

Hanan Alyami, Purdue University

Mahtob Aqazade, Purdue University

Signe E. Kastberg, Purdue University

Mathematics Education Researchers (MERs) contribute to the growth of mathematics education when joining interdisciplinary groups. However, we know little about ways of work and discourse within such groups. We explored practices reported by an MER during a semi-structured interview about her interdisciplinary group experiences. A grounded theory analysis resulted in identifying a collection of MERs' practices in interdisciplinary groups. We argue that when MERs are a part of interdisciplinary groups, they engage in practices that involve ways of being, operating, and interacting. MERs' awareness of practices in interdisciplinary groups contributes to the evolution of mathematics education as a field.

Williams et al. (2016) defined disciplinarity as a “phenomenon” involving “specialization” of work and discourse (p. 4). Members of interdisciplinary groups are practitioners of different disciplines who exhibit specialized forms of work and discourse, also called practices (Hyland, 2000; Williams et al., 2016). Prior definitions of practice include descriptions of methods for functioning within a group or community (e.g., Cobb & Yackel, 1996; McIntyre, 1984; Schön, 1983; Wenger, 1998). Based on existing literature, we describe practices as established or emergent ways of *being*, *operating*, and *interacting* with others during a collective activity (Suazo-Flores et al., 2021, para. 4). Ways of *being* refer to an individual's conceptualization of self as part of a group. Ways of *operating* refer to ways the group engages in an activity (e.g., regularity of meetings, participation expectations). Ways of *interacting* refer to the development and communication of a group's discourse norms.

Given that researchers use certain practices unique to their discipline, mathematics education researchers (MERs) may face challenges when interacting with researchers from other disciplines. For example, Bruce et al. (2017) described the academic challenge of framing a research idea within an interdisciplinary research team “in ways that permit all potential research collaborators to identify and situate themselves” (p. 158). Goos and Bennison (2018) described physical and institutional challenges such as traveling to different

Please cite as: Suazo-Flores, E., Walker, W. S., III, Alyami, H., Aqazade, M., & Kastberg, S. E. (2021). Understanding practices in an interdisciplinary group from a case study. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 3, pp. 986–994). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5416722>

disciplinary meeting venues and ensuring that interdisciplinary work contributed to achieving tenure. These reports describe considerations MERs might take up as they contemplate joining interdisciplinary groups. Building from our previous work, where we analyzed practices reported interdisciplinary groups' published research articles (Suazo-Flores et al., 2021), we continued exploring practices by studying a MER's experience in an interdisciplinary group.

Mathematics education as a discipline

MERs' practices draw from the discipline of mathematics education comprised by mathematics and psychology (Kilpatrick, 2014; Stinson & Walshaw, 2017). Described as the study of relationships between mathematics and human beings (Dörfler, 2003, p. 147), the discipline of mathematics education was developed in response to behaviorism (Kilpatrick, 2014). Early MERs were disciplinary experts in mathematics, psychology, education, and linguistics and theorized about mathematics curriculum, teaching, and learning. Currently, MERs often have degrees or specializations in mathematics education and research the traditional areas (e.g., mathematics curriculum, teaching, and learning). Additionally, MERs explore mathematics as a cognitive activity (Gómez, 2000; Kilpatrick, 2014; Valero, 2010) that involves human beings' minds and bodies (de Freitas, 2014), identities (Darragh, 2016), and sociopolitical and cultural surroundings (Gutiérrez, 2013; Valero, 2010). As the discipline of mathematics education continues to evolve, it enables and constrains MERs through sanctioned practices and inquiry domains. Valero (2010) described the boundaries of the discipline as moving to align with "ethical commitments" (p. LXXXV) of MERs' work and what the work can offer us and society. One way of expanding the boundaries of mathematics education research is to explore the products and processes involved in research practices (Ernest, 1998). An example of a product of interdisciplinary mathematics education research is the answers obtained from studying a topic using interdisciplinary lenses (e.g., Bruce et al., 2017). MERs' experiences in interdisciplinary groups are a special phenomenon, which is the goal of this study.

Mathematics education, interdisciplinary research, and practices

MERs collaborations with researchers from other disciplines to solve complex problems have expanded mathematics education research boundaries. Four examples from published articles are provided here. Bruce et al. (2017) explored how different disciplines (psychology, mathematics, and neuroscience) understand and study spatial reasoning. This work expanded mathematics education research boundaries by illustrating spatial reasoning's educational significance from multiple disciplinary perspectives. Goos and Bennison (2018) documented mathematicians' and mathematics educators' work in designing teacher education curriculum. The authors described collaborations between mathematicians and mathematics educators that provided opportunities to integrate mathematics content and pedagogy and resulted in curricula that benefited teacher candidates. Biology education researchers worked with an MER to study undergraduate biology students' graphing

practices in two different environments (Gardner et al., 2021). This collaboration added new insight into the common research problem of promoting graphing practices in new ways in mathematics education. Krummheuer et al. (2013) advanced the understanding of children's creativity when working with mathematical problems drawing from a socio-constructivist approach and a psychoanalytic perspective. The researchers used attachment theory to explore a student's activity when engaged with mathematical problems in a cooperative learning situation. Their findings described the working processes of creative children and expanded this to include the psychodynamic background's influence.

As interdisciplinary groups contribute to the evolution of mathematics education as a discipline, there is a need to explore practices used in interdisciplinary groups to support future MERs' interdisciplinary endeavors. Suazo-Flores et al. (2021) explored practices reported in published research articles. Findings included descriptions of three practices used in interdisciplinary collaborations: "working towards research interests," "cultivating trust and open-mindedness", and "understanding of institutional support." Because the aim of the published articles, used as data, was to communicate findings rather than to describe interdisciplinary practices, the practices identified were initial and tentative. This paper extends our prior work to illustrate practices experienced by MERs by asking: What are some representative practices described by an MER who participated in an interdisciplinary group?

Methods and analysis

This qualitative study is part of a larger project where we interviewed five MERs who were part of different interdisciplinary groups. We conducted semi-structured interviews (Kvale, 1996) to understand the practices that were a part of MERs' experiences in such groups. We present a case study (Flyvbjerg, 2011) of one of the five MERs (pseudonym Amelia), who was the leader of an interdisciplinary group. The transcript from Amelia's semi-structured interview constitutes the data for this study.

We used grounded theory (Charmaz, 2005) to analyze Amelia's descriptions of working in an interdisciplinary group. The analysis was done in three phases. In the first phase, we used our definition of practice as a conceptual framework to identify instances where Amelia described practices either she or the interdisciplinary group used. Each instance was coded as *being*, *interacting*, or *operating*. For example, the following excerpt was coded as an instance of a practice fitting into the *being* category.

Amelia: For me, it's been a wonderful growing experience. So I don't feel like I've lost anything because I still have my life in my discipline, and I have a much enriched and expanded life as well by having these experiences that I didn't realize I was going to get.

Amelia referred to her identity as an MER noting, "I still have my life in my discipline." She also recognized that her work in the interdisciplinary group had "enriched and expanded" her life. We identified this as a way of *being* because it provided evidence of her evolving identity as an MER through her work with people from other disciplines.

In the second phase, we used instances from the transcript to refine our descriptions and definitions of the *being*, *interacting*, and *operating* categories. We also created phrases that summarized the practices identified in each category. For instance, we created the phrase “perception of self as a leader in a discipline and compared to other disciplines” for the above piece of transcript. This analytical process allowed us to enhance our definition of practices as ways of *being*, *interacting*, and *operating* and identify a collection of practices within each category (findings reported in Suazo-Flores et al., in press). Once the revised definitions and collections of practices reached a saturation point, the third phase of analysis began. In this final phase, we used the revised definitions and collections of practices to re-code our data corpus, identifying and describing practices reported by Amelia.

Findings

Five representative practices are presented as findings for this research. We describe these as representative practices because they embody and allow us to communicate the main elements of the *being*, *interacting*, and *operating* categories. For the *being* and *interacting* categories we present one practice and three from the *operating* category. The five practices described in this report do not represent all possible practices.

Ways of being, view of others' roles

Practices in the *being* category refer to Amelia's description of her individual identity as a part of the group or how she perceived others as a part of a group (Suazo-Flores et al., in press). The practice includes being a member of the group and being in the sphere of the group's work. The following transcript excerpt was coded as evidence in the *being* category and assigned the phrase “view of others' roles.”

Amelia: So I wanted this to be a truly collaborative project where even though, you know obviously Chris [pseudonym] and I had in mind what we wanted to do, it wasn't nailed down. There had to be space there for everyone to contribute and to recognize complementary expertise. No one, no one knows everything. So that's, that was one thing I looked at as well.

Amelia referred to her identity as a leader in developing a proposal for the project and the identity of others within the group as collaborators. She intentionally wanted to make spaces for her colleagues' voices and create a “truly collaborative project.” She also described her views of others in the group by recognizing that everyone in the group had different knowledge and expertise when she said, “No one knows everythin.” We interpreted Amelia's words as evidence of how she conceptualized colleagues' roles in the interdisciplinary group.

Ways of interacting, build trust/respect

The practices in the *interacting* category refer to Amelia describing ways in which she and others in the interdisciplinary group: (1) developed and communicated standards for discourse related to the group or (2) negotiated the meanings of ideas, frameworks, representations, or phrases. The following transcript was identified as a practice in the

interacting category and assigned the phrase “build trust/respect.” Amelia expressed that her work in the interdisciplinary group “gave [her] opportunities to get to know people and to break down some of the barriers and the mistrust that had existed certainly in [place] for a very long period of time.” Amelia explained that “barriers” and “mistrust” interfered with people from different disciplines working together. We interpreted this excerpt as the group breaking down barriers by negotiating and reconstructing ideas, allowing people to start developing common understandings.

Ways of operating

The practices in the *operating* category refer to Amelia recounting ways of doing within the group. Included in this category are structures that allowed the group to conduct work like holding regular meetings, promoting a sense of community, identifying leadership roles, or stating that ideas like “open-mindedness” were important. *Operating* also includes understanding policies and actions from an outside group or institution that indicate the work’s value.

Having a common purpose

One practice identified in the *operating* category was assigned the phrase “having a common purpose,” which could take the form of a common goal or a research topic.

Amelia: The goal was to drive a major improvement in the quality of mathematics and science teachers by supporting new preservice programs in which faculty schools or departments of science, mathematics, and education collaborate on course design and delivery combining content and pedagogy. So that mathematics and science are taught as dynamic, forward looking, and collaborative human endeavours. So the whole purpose of the program is to get mathematicians and scientists working together with mathematics educators and science educators. Because the way secondary teachers are prepared in [place] is you come to the university, you learn the mathematics in the mathematics department, and at some other time, time you go to the opposite side of the campus and you learn how to teach the mathematics. And these two groups of people never talk to each other.

In the quote, Amelia recounted the goal that motivated the creation of the interdisciplinary endeavor; developing integrated curricula between mathematicians, scientists, mathematics educators, and science educators). Even though potential interdisciplinary group members might not know each other, there was a common purpose that motivated them to work as a part of the group.

Intentional team building

A second practice in the *operating* category was described as “intentional team building.” Amelia reported that her interdisciplinary group had understandings that allowed the group members to work with autonomy and in collaboration. These understandings encouraged the members of the group to work together as they used and shared existing experiences.

Understanding practices in an interdisciplinary group from a case study

Amelia: Everyone had tried something already to do something different in so that first meeting we started, well when we wrote the proposal actually, created a menu. So we were about menus and repertoires, not about mandates. So that was the menu that we've been trying. And then we each picked something from that menu that we decided to try this approach next year and then we swapped and learned from each other.

A way of collaborating within the interdisciplinary group was to create “menus” instead of “mandates.” This approach acknowledged the value of everyone’s knowledge and previous experiences, which allowed them to share and build from each other. Group members tried new ideas and shared their experiences with the redefined approach. The sharing of ideas allowed the interdisciplinary group to learn from each other and learn about working together as a team.

Understanding external constraints

A third practice in the *operating* category was assigned the phrase “understanding external constraints.” The way a group is positioned within and between other groups or institutions can afford or constrain work progress. For example, group/institutional policies could indicate the value of work being done by providing meeting space. In contrast, group/institutional policies could hinder interdisciplinary work by rejecting research because it uses unfamiliar methods for analysis. Amelia reported that it was important for her interdisciplinary group to be aware of institutional norms, make sense of the influence of these norms, and develop ways to operate within these norms.

Amelia: So I think our project was not so much about let’s have this grand design we’ll design this incredibly sophisticated expensive program and online packages and so on. And it was about thinking about the small changes that we can actually make that are not going to require layer upon layer upon layer of [institutional] approvals which we know is going to take a long time.

Amelia described how knowing how institutions operated allowed her to identify ways to work within those institutions. She knew that significant changes would require approvals from outside of the group. These institutional policies might discourage people involved in the interdisciplinary group’s work. She explained that the group focused on building from what people were already doing and making small changes that could result in significant improvements—this way of collaborating allowed the members to see their work in the interdisciplinary group as attainable and meaningful.

Although practices were identified in the *being*, *interacting*, and *operating* categories, we found that the categories were not mutually exclusive. Practices can align with the description of more than one category. For example, “understanding external constraints” can describe a way of *operating* and may include ways of *interacting* as people make sense of policies that exist with different groups. Practices in one category can also relate to or influence practices in another category. Like the prior example, “being open-minded” can describe a way of *operating*, but may include ways of *interacting* as people learn what it means to be open-minded. Below is a quote showing evidence of a practice that could be

classified in the *being* and *operating* categories. We identified this practice as “view of self in a discipline” and “having common goals or common research interests.”

Amelia: This project was not meant to be a research project but I was determined to build research into it because I wanted to understand, “How does the interdisciplinary piece work?” So you know the chief scientist, all he wanted was new approaches to teacher education but we thought, “No, let’s research this and try to work out what’s going on here.” So, and I think that all the team members found it very, very stimulating to be asked these kinds of questions.

In this excerpt, we see evidence of practices in the *being* and *operating* categories. Amelia shared her personal views of her role in the interdisciplinary project: “I was determined to build research into it.” She also reported how group members felt motivated to interact with each other around common goals and research.

Discussion and conclusion

We have identified representative practices in the *being*, *interacting*, and *operating* categories. Practices in the *being* category referred to MERs describing their view of themselves and others in the interdisciplinary group. Practices in the *interacting* category referred to ways of negotiating meaning of ideas and developing communication standards that allowed the group to collaborate. Practices in the *operating* category referred to mechanisms and group members’ ways of doing in the group to work together despite coming from different disciplines with specialized forms of work and discourse and navigating institutional constraints or policy.

The grounded theory approach allowed us to explore the categories of *being*, *interacting*, and *operating* further. We have expanded our original work (Suazo-Flores et al., 2021) by providing representative practices in each category from an MER’s experience in an interdisciplinary group. For instance, we now see the practice of “working towards research interests” as part of the practices in the *operating* category. “Having a common purpose”, “intentional team building”, and “understanding external constraints” were identified as additional practices in the *operating* category. Moreover, we now see “understanding institutional support” as an example of “understanding external constraints” and part of the practices in the *operating* category. The practice of “cultivating trust and open-mindedness” relates to researchers *interacting* in an interdisciplinary group in ways that allowed group participants to express themselves freely and consider the perspectives of others. We also found evidence that the categories are not mutually exclusive, which is evidence that understandings of the categories is still emerging.

One limitation of this study was the disproportionate number of practices identified in the *operating* category. The findings of our prior work (Suazo-Flores et al., 2021) resulted in practices that mainly fit with the *operating* category. These results influenced our interview protocol questions for this research and resulted in more opportunities for the participant to describe practices related to the *operating* category. A second limitation of this study is the interview data and analysis belonging to one case. We are analyzing more data to add more evidence from new cases. Future studies should explore practices in other interdisciplinary

groups or include observations of group members' interactions to expand our understanding of practices in the *being* and *interacting* categories.

As evidenced by our previous work (Suazo-Flores et al., 2021) and this paper, interdisciplinary groups involve MERs to developing practices in the *being*, *interacting*, and *operating* categories. MERs would benefit from being conscious of how they see themselves and how they see others as part of a group. For Amelia, it was important to preserve her identity as an MER. Amelia was able to direct her work to still contribute to her discipline while working in the interdisciplinary group. She also understood that no one knew everything in the group, which encouraged all group members to use and share their expertise and learn from each other. MERs also need to understand and identify ways to work within and among other groups or institutions. Amelia's group focused on making small and meaningful changes within the institutional structures. This allowed everyone in the interdisciplinary group to operate and feel sustained.

One of the benefits of MERs joining researchers from other disciplines is to solve more complex problems and expand mathematics education research boundaries. This study has shared evidence that MERs working in interdisciplinary groups also grow as individuals. Amelia recognized how much she learned from working with people from other disciplines and expanded her professional network. In reflecting on her experiences in interdisciplinary groups, Amelia noted:

Amelia: [This interdisciplinary work] means everything. It really means everything. I still can't believe this is where my career has ended up [...] there is something that we all care about, that might be a bit more important than each of us individually. That's the best thing that's ever happened to me in my life.

Amelia's interdisciplinary interactions allowed her to grow professionally as an MER and as a person, as evidenced when she said, "That's the best thing that's ever happened to me in my life."

Interdisciplinary work provides opportunities to expand the boundaries of mathematics education research. Identifying and developing interdisciplinary practices is one way to allow MERs and the discipline to grow. As MERs identify ways to feel sustained and free to pursue their research endeavors outside of the didactic triad (Valero, 2010), the field of mathematics education will continue extending its research boundaries. We showed evidence that when MERs are part of interdisciplinary groups, they engage in practices that involve ways of *being*, *operating*, and *interacting*. To feel sustained in interdisciplinary interactions, MERs need to be aware of who they are and how they see others in the group, negotiate and develop discourse standards, and identify ways to collaborate within and among their institutions and groups. Our research explores MERs' experiences in interdisciplinary groups and contributes a set of practices that MERs might use in their future interdisciplinary interactions.

References

- Bruce, C. D., Davis, B., Sinclair, N., McGarvey, L., Hallowell, D., Drefs, M., Francis, K., Hawes, Z., Moss, J., Mulligan, J., Okamoto, Y., Whiteley, W., & Woolcott, G. (2017). Understanding gaps in research networks: Using "spatial reasoning" as a window into the importance of networked educational research. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 95(2), 143–161. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-016-9743-2>

- Charmaz, K. (2005). Grounded theory in the 21st century: Applications for advancing social justice studies. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The Sage handbook of qualitative research* (pp. 507–536). Sage.
- Darragh, L. (2016). Identity research in mathematics education. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 93(1), 19–33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-016-9696-5>
- De Freitas, E., & Sinclair, N. (2014). *Mathematics and the body: Material entanglements in the classroom*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139600378>
- Dörfler, W. (2003). Mathematics and mathematics education: Content and people, relation, and difference. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 54(2-3), 147–171. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:EDUC.0000006118.25919.07>
- Ernest, P. (1998). A postmodern perspective on research in mathematics education. In A. Sierpiska & J. Kilpatrick (Eds.), *Mathematics education as a research domain: A search for identity* (pp. 71–85). Kluwer.
- Flyvbjerg, B. (2011). Case study. In N. Denzin & Y. Lincoln (Eds.). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research* (4th ed.). (pp. 301–316). Sage.
- Gardner, S., Suazo-Flores, E., Abraham, J. K., Karippadath, A., Meir, E., & Maruca, S. (2021). Biology undergraduate students' graphing practice in digital versus pen-and-paper graphing environments. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 30, 431–446. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-020-09886-w>
- Gómez, P. (2000). Investigación en educación matemática y enseñanza de las matemáticas en países en desarrollo. *Educación Matemática*, 12(1), 93–106.
- Goos, M., & Bennison, A. (2018). Boundary crossing and brokering between disciplines in pre-service mathematics teacher education. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 30(3), 255–275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13394-017-0232-4>
- Gutiérrez, R. (2013). The sociopolitical turn in mathematics education. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 44(1), 37–68.
- Kilpatrick, J. (2014). History of research in mathematics education. In Lerman, S. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of mathematics education* (pp. 349–354). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4978-8>
- Kvale, S. (1996). *Interviews: An introduction to qualitative research interviewing*. Sage.
- Stinson, D. W., & Walshaw, M. (2017). Exploring different theoretical frontiers for different (and uncertain) possibilities in mathematics education research. In J. Cai (Ed.), *Compendium for research in mathematics education* (pp. 128–155). National Council of Teachers of Mathematics
- Suazo-Flores, E., Alyami, H., Walker, W. S., III, Aqazade, M., & Kastberg, S. E. (2021). A call for exploring mathematics education researchers' interdisciplinary research practices. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13394-021-00371-0>
- Suazo-Flores, E., Walker, W. S., III, Alyami, H., Aqazade, M., & Kastberg, S. E. (in press). Conceptualizing practices in interdisciplinary groups from a mathematics education researcher's perspective. *Proceedings of the 43rd annual meeting of the North American Chapter of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education*. Philadelphia.
- Valero, P. (2010). Mathematics education as a network of social practices. In V. Durand-Guerier, S. Soury-Lavergne, & F. Arzarello (Eds.), *Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education* (pp. LIV–LXXX). Institut National de Recherche Pédagogique.
- Wenger, E. (1998). *Communities of practice: Learning, meaning, and identity*. Cambridge University Press.
- Williams, J., Roth, W. M., Swanson, D., Doig, B., Groves, S., Omuvwie, M., Borromeo Ferri, R., & Mousoulides, N. (2016). *Interdisciplinary mathematics education*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-42267-1>